

Evaluating a Multi-Camera Markerless System for Capturing Basketball-Specific Movements: An Exploration Using 25 Hz Video Streams

Supplementary Material

Contents

A. SUPPLEMENTARY METHODS	1
B. SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES.....	1
C. SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES.....	6

A. Supplementary Methods

A.1 Representative-Trial Selection for Waveform Plots

One paired trial was visualized to provide an intuitive illustration of temporal agreement between MMC and Vicon. This trial was selected a priori as a representative (non-outlier) case based on the distribution of trial-level validity metrics (e.g., median-level r and RMSE across joints) and the absence of missing axes. Importantly, all inferential statements in the main text are supported by the full set of paired trials and summarized quantitatively in Tables 2–5 and Supplementary Figures S6–S9.

A.2 Additional Quality Control and Exclusion Rules

Paired trials were identified by parsing subject/session/task identifiers from file names and matching MMC and Vicon files on a 1:1 basis. Frame-level alignment was performed using the synchronized event and a shared `frame_index`. Trials with missing joint-axis components were retained for analyses not involving the affected joint, but were excluded from frame-level agreement analyses requiring complete 12-joint data. Specifically, one paired trial had incomplete right-shoulder z coordinates in both systems; thus, right-shoulder trial-level summaries used $n = 41$, and this trial was excluded from pooled frame-level Bland–Altman analyses.

A.3 Signal Processing Details

All 3D joint trajectories were sampled at 25 Hz. To attenuate reconstruction jitter and reduce noise amplification in numerical differentiation, each axis component was low-pass filtered using a 4th-order Butterworth filter with a 6 Hz cutoff and zero-phase forward–backward filtering (`filtfilt`). Velocity and acceleration were then computed using central differences on the filtered displacement signals.

B. Supplementary Figures

B.1 Waveform Visualization

Figure S1. MMC vs. Vicon waveforms across 12 joints for velocity magnitude (v_mag) in a representative paired trial (25 Hz; 6 Hz low-pass filtered; zero-phase filtering). Solid lines indicate Vicon and dashed lines indicate MMC.

Figure S2. MMC vs. Vicon waveforms across 12 joints for acceleration magnitude (a_mag) in a representative paired trial (25 Hz; 6 Hz low-pass filtered; zero-phase filtering). Solid lines indicate Vicon and dashed lines indicate MMC.

B.2 Frame-Level Agreement Plots

Figure S3. Pooled Bland–Altman plot of frame-level agreement between MMC and Vicon for velocity magnitude (v_mag) across 12 joints (25 Hz; 6 Hz filtering). The center line denotes the mean bias and dashed lines denote the 95% limits of agreement.

Figure S4. Pooled Bland–Altman plot of frame-level agreement between MMC and Vicon for acceleration magnitude (a_mag) across 12 joints (25 Hz; 6 Hz filtering). The center line denotes the mean bias and dashed lines denote the 95% limits of agreement.

B.3 Distribution and Robustness Evidence

Figure S5. Task-level waveform validity across seven basketball-specific tasks.

Figure S6. Joint-wise distributions of waveform correlation (r) across all paired trials for displacement (pos_mag), velocity (v_mag), and acceleration (a_mag) magnitudes. Boxplots summarize the median and interquartile range, with whiskers indicating dispersion across trials.

Figure S7. Joint-wise distributions of waveform RMSE across all paired trials for displacement (pos_mag), velocity (v_mag), and acceleration (a_mag) magnitudes. Boxplots summarize the median and interquartile range, with whiskers indicating dispersion across trials.

Figure S8. Joint-wise distributions of waveform nRMSE% across all paired trials for displacement (pos_mag), velocity (v_mag), and acceleration (a_mag) magnitudes. Boxplots summarize the median and interquartile range, with whiskers indicating dispersion across trials.²

Figure S9. Joint-wise distributions of waveform scatter across all paired trials for displacement (pos_mag), velocity (v_mag), and acceleration (a_mag) magnitudes. Boxplots summarize the median and interquartile range, with whiskers indicating dispersion across trials.

C. Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Frame counts and valid-frame counts for each paired trial after alignment and differentiation (25 Hz; 6 Hz).

task	subject	session	frames_pos	frames_v	frames_a
Tri01	S01	Ses01	1352	1351	1350
Tri02	S01	Ses01	1111	1110	1109

Tri03	S01	Ses01	555	554	553
Tri04	S01	Ses01	1199	1198	1197
Tri05	S01	Ses01	823	822	821
Tri06	S01	Ses01	1771	1770	1769
Tri07	S01	Ses01	921	920	919
Tri01	S01	Ses02	1263	1262	1261
Tri02	S01	Ses02	1035	1034	1033
Tri03	S01	Ses02	588	587	586
Tri04	S01	Ses02	1076	1075	1074
Tri05	S01	Ses02	676	675	674
Tri06	S01	Ses02	1678	1677	1676
Tri07	S01	Ses02	936	935	934
Tri01	S02	Ses01	1181	1180	1179
Tri02	S02	Ses01	1013	1012	1011
Tri03	S02	Ses01	614	613	612
Tri04	S02	Ses01	978	977	976
Tri05	S02	Ses01	590	589	588
Tri06	S02	Ses01	1554	1553	1552
Tri07	S02	Ses01	850	849	848
Tri01	S02	Ses02	1113	1112	1111
Tri02	S02	Ses02	1013	1012	1011
Tri03	S02	Ses02	614	613	612
Tri04	S02	Ses02	994	993	992
Tri05	S02	Ses02	746	745	744
Tri06	S02	Ses02	1436	1435	1434
Tri07	S02	Ses02	900	899	898
Tri01	S03	Ses01	1078	1077	1076
Tri02	S03	Ses01	1110	1109	1108
Tri03	S03	Ses01	627	626	625
Tri04	S03	Ses01	1214	1213	1212
Tri05	S03	Ses01	862	861	860
Tri06	S03	Ses01	1850	1849	1848
Tri07	S03	Ses01	962	961	960
Tri01	S03	Ses02	1120	1119	1118
Tri02	S03	Ses02	1032	1031	1030
Tri03	S03	Ses02	595	594	593
Tri04	S03	Ses02	1046	1045	1044
Tri05	S03	Ses02	908	907	906
Tri06	S03	Ses02	1730	1729	1728
Tri07	S03	Ses02	944	943	942

Table S2. Log of missing joint-axis components detected during file merging and the corresponding handling strategy.

task	subject	session	joint	missing_cols
Tri01	S02	Ses02	R Shoulder	R Shoulder_z_vicon

Table S3. Sensitivity analysis of task-level waveform validity estimates with and without Tri06 (Layup, 3-step).

Variable	Task-level mean r_mean (All tasks, n=7)	Task-level mean r_mean (Excluding Tri06, n=6)	Δr	Task-level mean RMSE_mean (All tasks)	Task-level mean RMSE_mean (Excluding Tri06)	$\Delta RMSE$	RMSE change
pos_mag (m)	0.983	0.984	+0.001	0.103	0.060	-0.044	-42.3%
v_mag (m/s)	0.722	0.812	+0.090	0.957	0.379	-0.578	-60.4%
a_mag (m/s ²)	0.437	0.500	+0.063	22.694	9.418	-13.276	-58.5%

Notes:

(1) Task-level metrics (*r_mean*, *RMSE_mean*) were defined as in Table 3, i.e., averaged across joints and trials within each task. “All tasks” summarizes the mean across the 7 movement tasks (Tri01–Tri07).

(2) Tri06 (Layup, 3-step) was identified as an influential task because it showed simultaneously low task-level correlation and high task-level RMSE for derivative variables (*v_mag* and *a_mag*) relative to the across-task distribution. To quantify its influence on pooled task-level estimates, we recomputed the across-task means after excluding Tri06.

(3) Excluding Tri06 substantially reduced pooled task-level RMSE for *v_mag* and *a_mag* ($\approx 58\text{--}60\%$ reduction) and increased pooled task-level *r_mean*, indicating that derivative-variable agreement estimates are sensitive to this high-displacement, complex-posture task. The primary conclusions of the study remain unchanged (*pos_mag* shows the highest agreement, derivative variables exhibit larger errors), but derivative-variable results for Tri06 should be interpreted conservatively.

C.1 Sensitivity Analysis for Tri06 (Layup, 3-step)

To evaluate whether the task-level pooled validity estimates were unduly influenced by a single movement condition, we performed a sensitivity analysis focusing on Tri06 (Layup, 3-step). Tri06 exhibited the weakest derivative-variable agreement in the main results (Table 3), characterized by markedly reduced task-level waveform correlation (*r_mean*) and substantially inflated task-level error (*RMSE_mean*) for both *v_mag* and *a_mag*. Because derivative variables amplify small timing misalignments and reconstruction jitter, high-displacement and complex-posture tasks may act as influential conditions in pooled summaries.

Following a standard exploratory screening approach, Tri06 was treated as an influential task at the task level because it simultaneously presented low correlation and high RMSE compared with the across-task distribution (7 tasks). We therefore recomputed pooled task-level means across tasks for each magnitude variable using (i) all tasks (Tri01–Tri07) and (ii) excluding Tri06 only. Results are reported in Table S3.

Excluding Tri06 increased the pooled task-level correlation for *v_mag* (0.722 to 0.812) and *a_mag* (0.437 to 0.500), while markedly reducing pooled task-level RMSE (*v_mag*: 0.957 to 0.379 m/s; *a_mag*: 22.694 to 9.418 m/s²). The displacement magnitude (*pos_mag*) remained highly correlated regardless of inclusion, with a moderate reduction in pooled RMSE (0.103 to 0.060 m). Collectively, these findings indicate that derivative-variable validity estimates are sensitive to Tri06, whereas the overarching conclusion—high agreement for displacement and larger uncertainty for derivative variables—remains robust. Consequently, Tri06-specific derivative metrics should be interpreted conservatively, and reporting both full-task and sensitivity summaries improves transparency for applied deployment scenarios.

C.2 Concordance Correlation Coefficient (CCC)

To complement the Bland–Altman agreement analysis, Lin’s concordance correlation coefficient (CCC) was computed to quantify the overall concordance between MMC and the reference system (Vicon) at the frame level. CCC evaluates both precision (correlation) and accuracy (deviation from the identity line). Frame-level paired observations were pooled across the 12 joints and all valid frames/trials (consistent with the repeated-measures Bland–Altman dataset used in Table 4 of the main text). Table S4 summarizes CCC and Pearson’s *r* for the three magnitude variables.

Table S4. Frame-level concordance between MMC and Vicon across 12 joints (pooled joint-frame points).

Variable	N (joint-frame points)	Pearson <i>r</i>	Lin’s CCC	Mean difference (MMC–Vicon)
<i>pos_mag</i>	510,540	0.988	0.987	0.0029
<i>v_mag</i>	510,048	0.785	0.537	-0.0163
<i>a_mag</i>	509,556	0.701	0.477	-1.0451

C.3 Test–retest reliability of P95 and peak features

In addition to the mean feature reported in the main text, test–retest reliability was also evaluated for peak and 95th percentile (P95) features extracted from the magnitude time series (*pos_mag*, *v_mag*, *a_mag*). For each system and each trial, peak and P95 were computed from the filtered magnitude series, and reliability between Day 1 and Day 2 was assessed using ICC(A,1), CV%, and MDC95 (definitions consistent with the main text). To maintain concision in the main manuscript, only mean-feature summaries were included there; the peak and P95 summaries are provided here (Tables S5–S6).

Table S5. Summary of test–retest reliability for the peak feature (pooled across 12 joints × 7 tasks).

System	Variable	ICC(A,1) (median, range)	CV% (median, range)	MDC95 (median)
MMC	pos_mag	0.03 (-3.25–1.00)	2.92 (0.00–26.22)	0.133
MMC	v_mag	0.17 (-1.17–0.98)	4.66 (0.20–18.41)	0.361
MMC	a_mag	0.16 (-1.85–1.00)	7.05 (1.33–76.81)	3.935
Vicon	pos_mag	0.01 (-2.36–1.00)	2.92 (0.00–31.87)	0.186
Vicon	v_mag	0.13 (-1.09–1.00)	9.64 (0.50–141.34)	1.122
Vicon	a_mag	0.17 (-0.96–1.00)	15.63 (0.26–208.50)	33.230

Table S6. Summary of test–retest reliability for the P95 feature (pooled across 12 joints × 7 tasks).

System	Variable	ICC(A,1) (median, range)	CV% (median, range)	MDC95 (median)
MMC	pos_mag	0.03 (-9.85–1.00)	3.04 (0.00–35.49)	0.112
MMC	v_mag	0.36 (-0.88–0.98)	4.90 (0.39–34.44)	0.201
MMC	a_mag	0.38 (-1.48–1.00)	7.28 (1.23–42.03)	1.453
Vicon	pos_mag	0.02 (-1.43–1.00)	2.64 (0.00–37.55)	0.108
Vicon	v_mag	0.39 (-1.42–1.00)	5.25 (1.00–81.80)	0.221
Vicon	a_mag	0.33 (-1.49–1.00)	13.72 (0.47–200.19)	2.151

